

Solvent Effects on the Conductivity of Organic Compounds

M. F. MAYAHI AND H. A. HUSSAIN

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, University of Baghdad, Baghdad, Iraq

(Manuscript received 18 May 1972; accepted 10 November 1972)

Conductivity measurements have been used for the study of solvent-solute interactions. The conductivity of nitroethane in *n*-hexane and in triethylamine; and that of triethylamine in nitroethane and in nitrobenzene are reported. The effect of the dielectric constant on the conductivity of nitroethane, a proton-donor and of triethylamine, an electron-donor is shown in these systems.

A linear relationship is found between the logarithm of the specific conductivity and $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ for nitroethane-*n*-hexane, and for the pure compounds, methanol, ethanol, acetone and water.

Experimental

NITROETHANE and nitrobenzene were supplied by B.D.H., triethylamine was supplied by Merk Co., these compounds were fractionally distilled before use. *n*-Hexane, purous, was supplied by Fluka Co., and it was found to be non-conducting and was used as it is.

The following equation is used to calculate the dielectric constant (\bar{D}) of the solutions :

$$D_S = D_H + W(D_N - D_H) \quad (1)$$

where the subscript S refers to solution, H to *n*-hexane, and N to nitroethane. W is the weight fraction of nitroethane in solution. Apparatus and method is the same as that used before^{1,2}. Measurements were taken under atmospheric conditions.

Results and Discussion

In our study of the conductivity of hydrogen-bonded organic compounds, we reported the systems of alcohols in benzene¹, involving solute-solute interactions. The solvent effect on conductivity was reported on the system phenol-benzene and phenol-ether, where the participation of the hydrogen-bonded complex $C_6H_5OH \dots O(C_2H_5)_2$ was postulated². The systems reported in this paper involve stronger solvent-solute interactions; such interactions and their effect on conductivity have been discussed by Janz and Donyluk³.

Nitroethane (NE) in n-hexane: The conductivity of dilute solutions of NE in *n*-hexane does not change with increasing concentration of NE in the range $5.6 \times 10^{-2} - 50 \times 10^{-2}$ M/l, where nine different concentrations were used, and whose specific conductance at 14.5°C stayed at about 0.06×10^{-7} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹. However, the specific conductance of pure NE, which is 45.6×10^{-7} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹, decreased regularly as the compound was diluted with *n*-hexane. The results are shown in Fig. 1, measurements were taken until just before the solution separates into

two layers. The type of curvature obtained on plotting specific conductivity versus concentration

Fig. 1. Specific conductivity $L \times 10^7$ ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹ versus concentration C for nitroethane in *n*-hexane at 14.5°C.

M/l for NE-*n*-hexane system, Fig. 1, is similar to that reported by us for the alcohols-benzene systems¹. Since there is no interaction between solvent and solute, in this case then the conductivity must be accounted for by the "effective collisions" between NE molecules themselves, similar to the process visualized for the conductivity of alcohols in benzene¹.

The conductivity of NE-*n*-hexane solutions is related empirically to the dielectric constant (\bar{D}) of the solutions. This is done by the use of the equation

$$\ln L = \ln L_0 - U \frac{D-1}{2D+1} \quad (2)$$

where L and L_0 are the specific conductances in solvents of dielectric constants D and 1 respectively, U is a constant which is independent of the solvent^{4,5}. A linear relationship is found between log L and

$\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ with a slope of $-\frac{U}{2.3}$, Fig. 2 (and Fig. 4 for the pure solvents only). Fig. 2 shows that such a

plot is linear at 20°C and gently curved at 30°C. This curvature is due to the fact that NE and *n*-hexane are more miscible at 30°C than at 20°C, thus a wider range of concentrations, and therefore wider range of *D* is covered.

Fig. 2. Log specific conductivity L versus $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ for nitroethane in *n*-hexane solutions. Upper curve at 30°C., low curve at 20°C.

Nitroethane in triethylamine (TEA): The specific conductance of the solutions of NE in TEA decreases linearly with decreasing concentration of NE, Fig. 3. The very low values of L for such solutions (for pure

Fig. 3. Specific conductivity $L \times 10^7 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm.}^{-1}$ versus concentration, at 14.5°C., of nitroethane in TEA (o), of TEA in NE (x), and of TEA in nitroethane (o). (Using ΔL , the difference between L for solution and solvent, also gives same type of curves.)

TEA it is $24 \times 10^{-10} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm.}^{-1}$ at 14.5°C) indicates that the interaction between solvent and solute does not generate ionic species. Indeed ions will not be supported by solvents of low dielectric constant, D for TEA is 2.42 at 25°C. Therefore the linear change of L with concentration in such systems may be taken as an evidence or a criterion of weak interaction between solvent and solute. The species responsible for the conductivity in this system may be ion pairs between NE—TEA. This suggestion is parallel to

that proposed for the interaction between carboxylic acids and amines in benzene⁶.

Triethylamine in nitroethane: The specific conductance of the solutions of TEA in NE is greater than that of each pure liquid alone at 14.5°C. This increase in the value of L for the solutions indicates that there is a strong interaction between solvent and solute generating ionic charge-transfer complexes, that is, TEA is catalysing the ionization of NE as:

The formation of a complex is also indicated by the appearance of yellow colour on mixing of the two colourless components.

The dielectric constant of NE which is 26.8 at 14.5°C is not high enough to fully support and solvate ions as to separate them from each other by more than two or three molecular dimensions. Therefore the cation and the anion parts of the charge transfer complex will be hydrogen bonded to each other before they have a chance to be solvated away. Somewhat similar hydrogen bonded complexes have been proposed by Yerger and Barrow⁷ to exist between carboxylic acids and their anions in CCl_4 and in CHCl_3 .

Since NE may be self-associated (see NE in hexane) the ion formation will be aided by what may be termed the cooperative process, which is the stabilization of ions by the adjacent polarised molecules.

The concave graph obtained from plotting L versus concentration of NE, Fig. 3, is a criterion of strong solvent-solute interaction, and of the formation of ions.

Triethylamine in nitrobenzene (NB): This system was done so as to compare the conductivity of a system involving a proton transfer (TEA—NE) with one involving electron transfer as the TEA—NB system where TEA is a donor and NB is an electron acceptor. The specific conductance of TEA—NB solutions is greater than that for each pure liquid alone at 14.5°C. Fig. 3 (L for NB is $44.3 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm.}^{-1}$). The increase in L for the solutions indicates a strong interaction between the unshared pair of electrons of TEA with the benzene part of NB whose $D = 34.6$ at 25°C. From Fig. 3 it can be seen that the conductivity of TEA—NB system is greater than those of TEA—NE case.

The mechanism of the conductivity of the TEA—NB system may involve tunnelling of electrons, while that for the TEA—NE is purely ionic (or electrolytic). The mechanism involving tunnelling of electrons was used to account for the conductivity of organic compounds and their solutions^{1,2}. The TEA—NB system seems to be a case of such tunnelling, since electrons would be easily exchanged between the charge-transfer complex and its neighbouring molecules. The mechanism of this system would resemble that of solid organic dyes, in which exchange of electrons is known to be involved^{8,9}. Indeed the mechanism of the conductivity of pure NB is different from that

of water, methyl alcohol and acetone¹⁰; NB is regarded by Briere as an insulator.

The conductivity of pure compounds: Briere has measured, under N₂ atmosphere, the conductivity of water, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene¹⁰. These compounds were very carefully purified. Thus Briere's data are regarded as the best available in this field, where accurate data is lacking. We have treated Briere's data using our dielectric constant approach, equation (2). Fig. 4

Fig. 4. Log specific conductivity L versus $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ for the pure solvents: Water W , methylalcohol Me , ethylalcohol Et , acetone AC , and nitrobenzene NB , all at 25°C.

shows the plot of $\log L$ versus $\frac{D-1}{2D+1}$ for the pure compounds mentioned above. As expected a straight line is obtained, whose slope is $-\frac{U}{2.3}$, where it is

confirmed that U is a constant independent of the solvent^{4,5}. Nitrobenzene, as expected, does not fall on this line, Fig. 4, indicating that the mechanism of the conductivity of NB is different from that of the other compounds. The compounds involving tunnelling of electrons, as NB , would fall on a line separate from that for the compounds involving ionic (electrolytic) conduction, however, not enough accurate data are available for the "electron-tunnelling organic compounds" to construct their separate line. The conductivity of NB may be due to dissociation of impurities (nitrophenol)¹¹. However, the radical anion $C_6H_5NO_2^{\cdot-}$, as would be expected from electron tunnelling, has been observed by its esr spectra¹².

References

1. M. F. MAYAHI and A. E. HABBOUSH, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1965, **112**, 222.
2. M. F. MAYAHI and A. E. HABBOUSH, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1965, **112**, 224.
3. G. J. JANZ and S. S. DAMYLUK, "Electrolytes", p. 280, (Ed.) B. Pesce, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1962.
4. J. G. KIRKWOOD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **2**, 351.
5. C. REICHARDT, *Angew. Chem. Internat. Edit.*, 1965, **4**, 29.
6. S. BRUCKENSTEIN and A. SAITO, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 698.
7. E. A. YERGER and G. M. BARROW, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4474, 6204; G. M. BARROW, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 5802.
8. D. M. CARLTON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 2661.
9. A. TERENIN, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 321.
10. G. BRIERE, *An. Physique*, 1964, **9**, 73.
11. G. BRIERE and F. GASFARD, *Chem. Phys. Letters*, 1968, **1**, 706.
12. G. BRIERE, *J. Chim. Phys.*, 1969, **66**, 44.